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Regeneration processes in the *Pectoralis major* muscles of broiler chickens selected for different growth-rates: the importance of vimentin and desmin

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Vimentin and desmin in skeletal muscle

Distribution of VIM and DES in the skeletal muscle

[Banwell, 2001; *Pediatr. Neurol.* 24, 257-263]

Functions in skeletal muscle

- maintain sarcomeres' cytoarchitecture and integrity
- connection with organelles (including mitochondria and nuclei)
- Force transmission
- Mechanochemical signaling

Distinctive features

- Common structure and high homology
- Dynamic expression
- Co-assembly

Regeneration processes in skeletal muscle

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Vimentin and desmin are widely studied as **markers** of the **regenerative processes** occurring in skeletal muscles.

What about broilers' pectoral muscles?

DESMIN AND VIMENTIN IN REGENERATING MUSCLES

MUSCLE & NERVE 15:14-20 1992

ANTJE BORNEMANN, MD, and HENNING SCHMALBRUCH, MD

Desmin and Vimentin as markers of regeneration in muscle diseases

Acta Neuropathol (1992) 85: 88 - 92

A. Gallanti, A. Prella, M. Moggio, P. Ciscato, N. Checcarelli, M. Sciacco, A. Comini, and G. Scarlato

Our results suggest that vimentin and desmin may be expressed during muscle regeneration processes, probably because of their importance in the structural organization of the sarcomere, and are, therefore, a reliable marker of muscle fiber regeneration.

[Velleman and Clark, 2015; Avian Dis. 59,410-418]

Aim of the study

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Ascertain the **evolution** of **VIM** and **DES** in the *Pectoralis major* muscles of **modern chicken hybrids** selected for meat production and evaluate their potential **implication** in the **regeneration** processes occurring in the skeletal muscle.

Material and Methods

Experimental design

genotypes

sampling times (days post-hatch, D)

Sampling

Selection

Western Blot

Data analysis

Pectoralis major muscle

Freezing

H&E staining

N=5 muscles/genotype/sampling time

Protein extraction

SDS-PAGE and transfer

Immunoblot

Material and Methods

Statistical analyses

Within each sampling age (d7, d14, d21, d28, d35, and d42), the **non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test** was applied to assess the **effect of the genotype** (FG vs. MG) on the expression level of VIM and DES proteins.

For FG broilers, the **one-way ANOVA** option was used to evaluate the **evolution** of VIM and DES proteins **over the growth period**. Means were subsequently separated by using Tukey-HSD test.

All statistical differences were considered significant at a level of $p \leq 0.05$ and all the analyses were performed by using Statistica 10 (StatSoft Inc., 2014).

Results

Representative image of the immunoblots obtained for vimentin and desmin

Heterodimeric form

Native protein

..the type III proteins can **assemble** into filaments containing only a single polypeptide (e.g., vimentin) or consisting of two different type III proteins (e.g., vimentin plus desmin).

[Cooper, 2000]

Results

Vimentin

Native protein

Heterodimeric form

* and ** = within the same age, mean values significantly differ between FG and MG for a p-value <0.05 and <0.01, respectively. a-c = for FG, mean values followed by different letters significantly differ over the growth period (p<0.05).

Results

Desmin

Native protein

Heterodimeric form

* and ** = within the same age, mean values significantly differ between FG and MG for a p-value <0.05 and <0.01, respectively. a-c = for FG, mean values followed by different letters significantly differ over the growth period (p<0.05).

other outcomes..

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Investigating differences of *Pectoralis Major* muscle *Vimentin* and *Desmin* gene expression between broilers selected for different growth-rates

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Aims of the study

- Evaluating the normalized gene expression levels of *Vimentin* (VIM) and *Desmin* (DES) chicken genes looking at multiple steps of *Pectoralis major* (PM) muscle development in **fast- (FG) and medium- (MG) growing** male broilers;
- Assessing the potential involvement of VIM and DES in **muscle regeneration** characterizing broilers selected for rapid growth and affected by **growth-related abnormalities** (White Striping and Wooden Breast) as hypothesized in the literature*.

Conclusive remarks

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- **First attempt** to investigate the expression of VIM and DES over the growth period (from 7 to 42 d of age) in FG and MG broiler chickens and **confirmed** their **potential use as markers** of the **regenerative processes** occurring in skeletal muscle.
- Support the existence of a **relationship** between the occurrence of **muscle regeneration** and the **growth rate** of the meat-type chickens with the FG hybrids being more susceptible to this phenomenon (as well as to the occurrence of growth-related muscle defects).
- VIM and DES could be **potentially exploited as molecular markers** to identify breeders bearing/prone to develop the growth-related abnormalities and exclude them from the breeding practices, thus improving the economic and environmental sustainability of the system.

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